

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Online at: www.iajps.com

Research Article

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN CHILDREN DURING THE PANDEMIC (COVID-19)

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Article Received: March 2021

Accepted: March 2021

Published: April 2021

Abstract:

Since childhood physical education, sports and power activities figure in every person's life. As a child develops, parents send him or her to sports sections of different orientation: gymnastics, soccer, athletics, boxing, etc. The formation of such a habit as a hobby physical activity is carried out not only to occupy their free time, but mainly to ensure normal physiological development, improve the functional processes of the growing organism, as well as strengthen the immune system and the overall health of the child. With age, children may change their hobbies, change sports or engage in art and creativity, but moderate loads still remain in their lives, such as school physical education classes or student physical education classes, which continue for almost the entire period of study: from 1 to 9 (11) grade and 1 to 3 (5) year, respectively. This is due to the fact that sport and human health are in close relationship, as physical activity provides good body condition, improves mental and psychological development, strengthens immunity, has a general preventive effect on the body. That is why regular exercise is so important. The paper considers the problems of forming a healthy lifestyle in children and provides recommendations for overcoming them, also considered the statistics of public health to emphasize the relevance of the topic, also this article focuses on the pandemic (COVID-19), its impact on physical activity, pupils, students, employees and other citizens. The reasons that led to a decrease in motor activity of citizens, as well as some recommendations to avoid the worst consequences.

Key words: healthy lifestyle, health, health risk factors, pandemic(COVID-19), coronavirus, physical education, self-isolation, maintaining physical fitness.

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QR code

Please cite this article in press Ilyakhina O.U et al., *Physical Activity And Psychological And Pedagogical Recommendations For The Formation Of A Healthy Lifestyle In Children During The Pandemic (Covid-19).*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(04).

INTRODUCTION:

For the successful activity of a student, cadet and listener, constant maintenance of muscular and cerebral activity is necessary. Motor activity is a natural need of the body. Normal vital activity of the cardiovascular, respiratory, neuroendocrine systems and body tissues in general is possible only with a certain organization of diverse muscular activity. The development of the musculoskeletal system and the prevention of posture disorders create all the conditions for normal growth and development of the human body. All this shows that some physical activity is an important aspect of the formation of all human health in general.

However, in today's world the problem of health and low motor activity of young people, which itself is very complex and requires a comprehensive approach to its solution, is becoming increasingly important. "Students, cadets and trainees of higher educational institutions are more susceptible than others to various chronic diseases", which is important to prevent at the stage of the appearance of the first symptoms. This is expressed in the fact that student activity is associated with a large workload in classrooms, low motor activity, especially senior courses, improper nutrition, insufficient recovery and sometimes psychological overload, which leads to a decline in health.

In addition, at the present time on the psychological and physical state of the person is negatively affected by many adverse factors, such as: bad ecology, the emergence of gadgets and cars, the lack of outdoor exercise, poor quality food and bad habits. All this primarily affects health, weakening and worsening it. That's why it's so important to strengthen the body's defenses with preventive measures aimed at strengthening the immune system, as well as with physical activity.

Small physical activities done every day or several times a week have an impact on the overall performance of students, cadets and trainees.

"Recreational and supportive exercise creates an adequate supply of oxygen to the body, this leads to a stabilization of the metabolism. Muscular activity also improves lymphatic flow, which is critical for eliminating toxins from the body." Particular attention should be paid to the fact that an increase in the intensity of exercise, if not properly evaluated by students, can lead to its uselessness or have a negative impact at all. However, "the better the state of health and the higher the level of preparedness of a person for various physical activities, the greater his resistance to intellectual fatigue, and as a consequence, the more pronounced are the effects of physical activity.

Purpose of the study:

For a more detailed elaboration of the issue of maintaining one's health, it will be advisable to conduct various surveys in which it will be possible to assess the knowledge of the younger generation in matters of healthy lifestyle and then determine the main directions of work with them. It also happens that the child is not at all interested in his health. In this case he needs an example, and it is desirable that this example serve as family members with whom the child has a sufficiently close connection and attachment, as well as infinite trust.

However, despite the large number of listed means of education, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in children is a complex, developing object, so there is a need to use a multidimensional approach. It is no secret that one of the main sources of health deterioration is stress. What can it be caused by? First of all it is necessary to pay attention not to the failures that are waiting for people at every step, but to the person's self-esteem, his inner attitude towards himself. Someone will take a small trifle as an insurmountable obstacle, while for someone and serious problems will be a motivation for self-development. The vast majority of members of society have low self-esteem. This fact is quite depressing.

RESEARCH METHODS:

The educational process, providing orderly formation of healthy lifestyle culture of schoolchildren together with the development of other human qualities, the totality of which crucially determines its mental and physical components, gives individual development the features of a purposeful process and is the main in familiarizing the individual to a healthy lifestyle.

Formation of healthy lifestyle culture of schoolchildren and preschool children in the educational space of school and preschool educational institutions is a determining basis for harmonious development of the student's personality, his way of life and active life position.

This process will be more effective with the implementation of the following pedagogical conditions:

- consideration of the value attitude to health and healthy lifestyle as a target and content component of the educational process of the educational institution;
- inclusion in the basis of the educational process of the educational institution of mastering by students the basics of a healthy lifestyle, necessary in socio-personal, mental and physical plan to improve the effectiveness of professional education and implementation in the future effective professional activities;
- implementation of a comprehensive solution to the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle in the educational process;
- implementation of differentiated and individualized selection of the content, forms and methods of formation of a healthy lifestyle taking into account the peculiarities of the students' contingent involved in the activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Of particular importance is the rationality and correctness of selected physical training. Before, during, and after the end of any intellectual activity one can trace the dynamics of intensity of brain work capacity. Establishing exactly that level of motor activity, which is the most effective in achieving the maximum mental index, is important here. Full recovery of the organism is possible only if the level of physical activity corresponds exactly to the general preparedness of the person. Moreover, it is worth considering the fact that insignificant loads will not have the planned effect, and excessive ones, on the contrary, will not allow the body to fully recover, which will lead to a decline in performance. Regular exercise is one of the easiest and most effective ways to affect the well-being and condition of a person, as well as keeping him in good physical shape to ensure

the full development and performance of all work tasks. Moreover, a particularly important fact is that the exercises performed should bring a sense of satisfaction and joy from doing them, rather than excessive tension or protest, then both the productivity and the effect of the exercise will be much greater.

Thus, we can conclude that physical activity is an integral part of modern human life, an important element of normal development, functioning and existence, as well as an essential part of a healthy lifestyle. Sports have a special importance for students in educational organizations, as it directly affects the work of the brain and general intellectual activity. Physical development and maintenance is one of the most effective and affordable ways to protect your body from the adverse factors of the modern world around you. One of the most pressing concerns of modern society is the maintenance of health at a high level. Having studied the statistics, we can come to disappointing conclusions. For example, as of 2018 we can note a decrease in the birth rate by 5.4% compared to the previous year, in addition, in 32 subjects of the Russian Federation there was a rapid increase in mortality rates. Highlighted 6 main causes of deaths, and among them in the first place - diseases of the circulatory system, then - neoplasms, external causes, diseases of the nervous system, diseases of the digestive system, as well as respiratory. [State report on the implementation of state policy in the field of health for 2018]

It's not hard to guess that most diseases are caused by an unhealthy lifestyle, which can include poor diet and bad habits.

To maximize the elimination of unhealthy lifestyles, the right priorities should be instilled from a person's earliest age. As you know, the primary institution of socialization of the individual is the family: in many ways, the future life of the child is determined by his upbringing in the family, including his way of life. It is the family that performs the functions that largely determine a person's healthy physiological and psychological state.

And what is understood by health? Turning to Ozhegov's dictionary, we will find there the following interpretation: "The proper, normal activity of the organism, its complete physical and mental well-being. Accordingly, to maintain such a state of the body, it is necessary to follow certain recommendations, the totality of which forms the

well-known concept - HEA, which is constantly talked about: in kindergartens, schools, universities.

Why there? The above-mentioned institutions are the next institutions of personality socialization, especially schools and universities, to which children come at a fairly advanced age. It is during this period that they need an explanation of the necessary qualities, habits, actions, as rules for organizing their behavior. In this case, the role of the teacher is particularly high: the essence is not only to illuminate these aspects, but precisely to interest the younger generation, to form a reverent attitude to their health, as well as the health of their loved ones. All this is achieved through conversations, various thematic games, discussions, projects, problem solving, and more. In the process, it is desirable to use different ways of conducting classes - with the help of audio-visual accompaniment, performing various kinds of practical exercises, involving medical personnel, older children, etc. Successful assimilation of theoretical knowledge is provided by such means of education as teaching aids, posters, visual aids, games, videos, etc.

It is difficult enough to retrain an adult to treat himself/herself differently, for this, first of all, must be a desire to change his/her life for the better. A slightly different strategy with children - their psyche is not formed at a young age, it does not seem difficult to direct the orientation in the right direction. Thus, first of all, it is necessary to start not with the theory of a healthy lifestyle, physical training - all this will simply be useless without a person's desire to be healthy, but with the direction of internal orientation of the person to a proper attitude to himself, and, as a consequence - to his health. According to the researchers of the World Health Organization, the main risk factors for health are:

- 1) Psychological (the importance of the psychological component for the normal functioning of the body has been discussed in detail above);
- 2) Ecological (unfortunately, the ecological situation in our country leaves much to be desired, the state needs to develop more intensive and severe methods);
- 3) Social (here it is worth noting the importance of the environment that influences a person; however, everyone knows that if there is "something wrong" with the environment, the problem is in the person himself, because only he himself attracts such environment to himself);
- 4) Hereditary.

Recently, a new socio-cultural paradigm of health has begun to take shape, which has become a synthesis of

medicine, education, and culture. Its basic principles are: human responsibility for one's health, self-monitoring of one's health and development, conscious health-improving activities, the emotional beginning in the psychophysical development of personality, the program of formation of a healthy personality from conception to old age.

At the beginning of 2020 our country was completely taken over by the COVID-19 pandemic, the so-called pandemic of coronavirus infection. This event had a significant impact on the daily activities of citizens and organizations. Studies have found that the virus is transmitted through close contact with an infected person, particularly through airborne droplets when coughing, sneezing, and talking.

On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization declared this outbreak a public health emergency of international concern and on March 11, a pandemic.

On March 30, Russia's borders were completely closed. President Vladimir Putin announced the introduction of a non-working day regime. As it turned out later, this regime will be in effect for more than a month - until May 11. People were advised to stay at home all the time, leaving their homes only to buy basic necessities and go to work.

Subsequently, most educational institutions continued to work remotely for about a year, all mass events and activities of sports sections were suspended. Everyone was strongly advised to stay at home and leave it only when absolutely necessary - for groceries or to go to work. Many people diligently complied with this requirement and switched to the life of a homebody. All these factors greatly affected the physical culture of society.

Physical culture in this period of time lost its core value as many obstacles were created on the part of the government for the good of society to confront the COVID-19 pandemic. Most schoolchildren, students, office workers were transferred to remote work in the place of residence, thus the motor activity of these individuals decreased significantly, because not many people are willing to warm up their muscles and exercise at home instead of relaxing on the couch watching a movie.

CONCLUSION:

Physical education is based on developing and improving the physical abilities of the motor system and maintaining the body in a healthy state.

Medical experts believe that in order to maintain the body's previous physical endurance and metabolic processes, one should not radically change the lifestyle and level of physical activity. In case of violation of this prescription, a person can be subjected to rapid weight gain, obesity, wasting of physical abilities, premature aging and possible development of cardiovascular diseases.

Exercising at home has its advantages, such as:

Saving money for both travel and trainer and other expenses;

Saving the time it takes to go to the gym and back;

Suitable for shy and withdrawn people, no one is watching;

Comfort;

Freedom to choose the time of exercise and their type, which is easily freely available on the Internet.

Therefore, under any circumstances, you should not forget about physical culture, which is inherent versatility and mobility. With enough desire you will always be able to find a way to exercise and time for it. And it should be remembered that stable physical activity is necessary for the normal functioning of the body.

Speaking about the health of the younger generation, the main reason for the negative dynamics is the fact that about 75% of their free time pupils and students spend in educational institutions, and this happens systematically. A possible solution would be to unload children from educational institutions, for this purpose it is necessary to revise the educational program, reducing the time spent in educational institutions from 75% to 50%, which can be achieved by introducing some topics of training sessions for self-preparation, in the form of watching a video, passing the quest, etc.

We should not forget about the fact that students spend a lot of time in educational organizations on the computer. It is necessary in such classes to allocate time to rest, literally 5-7 minutes every 40 minutes for eye warming, as well as provide jobs hygiene means - antiseptics, wet wipes, etc.

To summarize, we can note that the culture of a healthy lifestyle has a huge impact not only on the physical fitness of the person and his state of health, but also on his priorities, self-esteem, which determines the socialization of the person and his self-realization in the future. It is worth noting that people who are introduced to the culture of a healthy lifestyle have a positive impact on others, thereby spreading the main paradigms of the culture of a healthy lifestyle.

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